

THE PROTECTIVE EFFECT OF SPIRONOLACTONE ON ISCHEMIA/ REPERFUSION INJURY IN RAT OVARY

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Keywords

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to investigate the potential protective effect of spironolactone against ischemia/reperfusion injury (IRI) in rat ovaries. Twenty-four female rats were randomly assigned to four groups (6 rats per group) for the administration of the study drug, spironolactone: Control (C), Ischemia (I), Ischemia-Reperfusion (I-R), and spironolactone-treated (IR-S) groups. The study group underwent bilateral ovarian ischemia for 4 hours, followed by 4 hours of reperfusion, with the initiation of IRI and daily oral administration of spironolactone (100 mg/kg) for three consecutive days before ischemia induction. Additionally, administration was scheduled 30 minutes before the reperfusion phase. Histological examination using hematoxylin and eosin staining was conducted to assess hemorrhage and edema scores, and immunostaining with Cysteine-aspartic protease 3 (Caspase 3), Microtubule-associated protein 1A/1B-light chain 3B (LC3B) Interleukin-1 beta (IL-1 β), and Tumor Necrosis Factor alpha (TNF- α). The results revealed that spironolactone treatment significantly reduced histological damage and monocyte count in the IR-S group compared to the I and I-R groups ($p < 0.05$). Our findings suggest that spironolactone exerts a protective effect against ovarian IRI in rats. This protection may be attributed to its antioxidant, vasodilatory effects, and anti-inflammatory properties, collectively contributing to preserving tissue integrity and function.

INTRODUCTION

Ovarian torsion is a phenomenon in which the ovary becomes twisted around its supporting ligaments in the adnexal region¹. It can occur due to various diseases, such as neoplasms and ovarian cysts. Approximately 80% of affected individuals are younger than 50 years old². Consequently, women of reproductive age are at the highest risk of experiencing torsion. Nevertheless, torsion can still occur in regular ovaries, especially among children. Pregnant women and those undergoing fertility treatments face a significant risk due to the presence of enlarged follicles on the ovary¹. This poses a genuine surgical crisis that, if not promptly detected, can lead to tissue death, ovarian loss, and infertility. Diagnosing ovarian torsion can be challenging because its symptoms are unclear, and laboratory tests and imaging results are not specific.

Following the correction of tissue torsion, there is a possibility of restoring blood flow, alleviating ischemic conditions by facilitating tissue recirculation and reperfusion. However, it is crucial to note that this process may also result in adverse outcomes, such as reperfusion injury^{3,4}.

Ischemia, followed by the restoration of blood flow to the tissue, known as reperfusion, triggers the release of reactive oxygen species, leading to increased inflammation in the tissue. These molecules can cause harm to cell membranes, exacerbating impairment of tissue function³. Karakas et al.⁴ reported that pretreatment with metformin, well-known for its antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties, is helpful in protecting against oxidative damage in ovarian tissue. Numerous drugs with antioxidant and anti-inflammatory effects have been studied to minimize damage to ovarian tissue in cases of ovarian torsion.

Spironolactone exhibits anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and vascular endothelial-regulating effects. Originally developed as a diuretic and antihypertensive agent, spironolactone has attracted attention beyond its conventional use due to its pleiotropic effects⁵. Aldosterone antagonists have shown

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favorable outcomes in experimental models of Ischemia-Reperfusion (I-R), including cerebral⁶, retinal⁷, hepatic⁸, gastrointestinal tract⁹, cardiovascular diseases¹⁰ and renal disorders¹¹.

Despite these findings, there has not been a study investigating the protective role of spironolactone in the context of ovarian reperfusion injury. This study aims to provide a comprehensive overview of the current understanding of ischemia/reperfusion injury (IRI), the intricate mechanisms driving ovarian susceptibility to such injury, and the potential protective role of spironolactone. By synthesizing existing literature and highlighting recent advancements, we aim to contribute to the growing body of knowledge aimed at preserving ovarian health and fertility in the face of ischemic challenges. As we delve into the multifaceted interactions involving spironolactone, our goal is to shed light on its potential as a protective agent in the context of ovarian reperfusion injury.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experimental Animals

In this study, 24 female adult Wistar Albino rats, weighing between 150 and 250 g and aged between 10 and 15 weeks, were included. The experimental procedures were carried out at the Animal Research Laboratory, Cumhuriyet University. The rats were given food ad libitum and were housed in a controlled environment, maintaining a temperature of $22 \pm 2^\circ$ C and controlled humidity, following a 12-hour light and dark cycle. To ensure the ethical and responsible use of animals in research, the committee recommended reducing each group to 6 rats, in line with the principles of the 3Rs (Replacement, Reduction, and Refinement) as outlined by Russell and Burch¹². This approach was adopted to minimize the overall use of rats¹³. Approval for the study protocol was obtained from the Ethical Committee on Animal Research at Cumhuriyet University (Approval No. 560).

Surgical procedures and groups

The female rats were randomly allocated into four groups (n=6):

1. **Control (C) group:** The abdominal wall was opened and then closed. Ovarian torsion and detorsion were not performed.
2. **Ischemia (I) group:** Underwent laparotomy for ovarian

ischemia. Ischemia was induced by clamping the bilateral ovarian arteries for 4 hours, followed by bilateral oophorectomy.

3. **Ischemia-Reperfusion (I-R) group:** Ischemia was induced by clamping the bilateral ovarian arteries for 4 hours, followed by reperfusion through releasing the clamps for 4 hours. No medication was administered to the rats. Bilateral oophorectomy was performed.
4. **Spironolactone-treated (IR-S) group:** Rats were orally administered 100 mg/kg of spironolactone via orogastric tubes for three consecutive days. On the 4th day, bilateral ovarian torsion was performed. Thirty minutes before the ovarian detorsion operation, the rats were given a single dose of 100 mg/kg peroral (p.o.) spironolactone. Detorsion was applied after 4 hours of ischemia, and bilateral oophorectomy was performed after 4 hours of detorsion. Spironolactone (Lot No: SLBC1964, Sigma Aldrich, China) was dissolved in 1 mL of saline for administration.

Spironolactone Treatment: The experimental group received a daily oral administration of spironolactone (100 mg/kg) for three consecutive days before ischemia induction. Additionally, administration was scheduled 30 minutes before the reperfusion phase. In determining the dose of Spironolactone for our study, we referred to a previous study that investigated the protective effect of a 100 mg/kg dose of Spironolactone in I-R.¹⁴ This study found that a dose of 100 mg/kg exhibited a protective effect without causing adverse histopathological changes in the liver and kidneys of rats. Therefore, we decided to use the same dosage in our study to ensure consistency and comparability with previous research. We believe this approach strengthens the validity of our findings.

Rats were anesthetized using a combination of ketamine hydrochloride (50 mg/kg Ketalan; VEM İlaç San. ve Tic. A.Ş., Istanbul, Turkey) and xylazine hydrochloride (10 mg/kg Rompun; Bayer Türk İlaç Ltd., Istanbul, Turkey). Subsequently, the abdominal area was shaved and prepared with a povidone-iodine cleansing solution. A laparotomy was performed by creating a 20 mm longitudinal incision in the central region of the lower abdomen, exposing the uterine horns and adnexa for observation. Ischemia was induced for a duration of 4 hours using a torsion model, achieved by the application and subsequent 720-degree rotation of atraumatic

vascular clips in a clockwise manner to the vascular pedicle, positioned 1 cm above and below each ovary bilaterally. This procedure was consistent with methodologies employed in previous investigations⁷. The closure of the abdominal wall, involving the musculoaponeurotic layer and the skin, was performed using 3-0 Vicryl (polyglactin 910, Ethicon, Somerville, New Jersey).

Following the initial surgical intervention, bilateral oophorectomy was conducted in all groups to facilitate histological scoring and hematological assessment. To evaluate hematological markers, a 5-mL blood sample was extracted from the vena cava of each rat. The rats were sacrificed by an overdose of anesthetic usage.

Biochemical analyses

Blood samples were collected using K3EDTA evacuated plastic tubes from Becton Dickinson in Franklin Lakes, NJ, USA. These samples were subsequently analyzed using XN-9000, a device manufactured by Sysmex Co. in Kobe, Japan, all within a 2-hour window from the time of collection. The

primary objective of this study is to assess the Complete Blood Count (CBC) parameters related to monocytes (MO). These parameters provide insights into cell intricacy, fluorescence strength, cell size, and the spread of events measured along the three axes of the white cell differential (WDF) channel. Specifically, the study evaluated the monocytes cells complexity [MO-X(ch)], the complexity and spread of events measured in, monocytes complexity and width of dispersion of the events measured [MO-WX], and the fluorescence intensity of monocytes [MO-Y(ch)].

Histopathologic Method

Necropsies were performed on the rats to identify ovarian tissues, which were subsequently immersed in a 10% neutral formalin solution. The tissues underwent standard processing steps involving alcohol and xylene before being embedded in paraffin blocks. Sections of 5 µm thickness were obtained on poly-lysine-coated slides and stained with hematoxylin-eosin. Six randomly selected areas were then evaluated for hemorrhagic and edematous changes based on the criteria outlined in Table 1.

Table 1. Histopathologic scoring.

Hemorrhage	Edema
No (-)	No (-)
Whole area <10% (+)	Whole area <5% (+)
Whole area 10-30% (++)	Whole area 5-10(++)
Whole area 30%>(+++)	Whole area 10%>(+++)

Immunohistochemical Method

The 5 µm sections, mounted on polylysine-coated slides, underwent sequential immersion in xylene and a series of alcohol solutions. Following this, a Phosphate buffer saline (PBS) wash was conducted, and subsequently, endogenous peroxidase activity was quenched by subjecting the sections to a 10-minute treatment with 3% H₂O₂. To expose antigens in the tissues, an antigen retrieval solution was applied for 2x5 minutes at 500 watts. Subsequently, the tissues were washed with PBS and incubated overnight at +4°C with primary antibodies Cysteine-aspartic protease 3 (Caspase 3) (ElabScience, Catalog No. E-AB-30004), Microtubule-associated protein 1A/1B-light chain 3B (LC3B) (Santa Cruz, Catalog No. sc-271625), Interleukin-1 beta (IL-1β) (Santa Cruz, Catalog No. sc-52012), and Tumor Necrosis Factor alpha (TNF-α) (Santa Cruz, Catalog No. sc-133192) at a dilution

ratio of 1/200.

For the secondary step, the Large Volume Detection System: anti-Polyvalent, Horseradish Peroxidase (HRP) (Thermofisher, Catalog No. TP-125-HL) was utilized as recommended by the manufacturer. 3,3'-Diaminobenzidine (DAB) served as the chromogen. Following counterstaining with Mayer's Hematoxylin, the sections were covered with Entellan and examined under a light microscope. Immunopositivity in the examination was semiquantitatively assessed as absent (-), mild (+), moderate (++) , and severe (+++).

Statistical Analysis

The obtained histopathological and immunohistochemical data underwent analysis using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) 20.00 software. Discrepancies between the

different groups were assessed using the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test, and identification of the specific group contributing to the observed variance was achieved through the Mann-Whitney U test. A p-value of < 0.05 was deemed statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

RESULTS

Hematological, histopathological, and immunohistochemical parameters were systematically evaluated to assess the effectiveness of spironolactone in mitigating IRI in rat ovaries.

Figure1. displays Hemoragia ve edema scores of rats study groups.

Ischemia (I), Ischemia-Reperfusion (I-R), Ischemia-Reperfusion -Spironolactane (IR-S)

Data were expressed as mean ± standard deviation (SD)

^{a,c} $p < 0.05$, vs C groups, I groups and I-R groups.

^{b,d} $p < 0.05$, vs I groups and IR groups.

Fig 1. illustrates the histopathological examination of ovary tissues in the rats' C, I, I-R, and IR-S groups. Upon visual observation of the C group, the ovaries exhibited a normal

histological appearance. The control group significantly reduced the hemorrhagic and edema scores compared to the I group, I-R group, and IR-S group ($p < 0.05$). The IR-S group significantly decreased the hemorrhagic and edema scores compared to the I group and I-R group ($p < 0.05$). Hemorrhagic and edema scores were significantly higher in the rats' I group and I-R group compared to the C group and IR-S group ($p < 0.05$). However, there were no significant differences concerning the hemorrhagic and edema scores between the I group and I-R group ($p > 0.05$) (**Fig 1, Fig 2**).

Figure 2. Presentative histopathological images of ovarian tissues obtained from rats study groups (hematoxylin and eosin, original magnification $\times 100$ for all figures). **A- C group.** Normal histological appearance, **B- (I) grubu.** Hemorrhage (\square) and edema (*) at a severe level, **C- (I-R) grubu.** Hemorrhage (\square) and edema (*) at a severe level, **D- (IR-S) grubu.** Hemorrhage at mild level.

Figure 3. Displays Histopathological examination of ovarian tissues of Caspase-3, LC3B, IL-1β, TNF-α staining scores groups.

Ischemia (I), Ischemia-Reperfusion (I-R), Ischemia-Reperfusion Spironolactane (IR-S). ^{a,c,e,g}p < 0.05, vs C groups, I groups and I-R groups. ^{b,d,f,h}p < 0.05, vs I groups and I-R groups.

Data were expressed as mean ± standard deviation (SD).

Figure 4. A-C group. Immune negativity, B- (I) group. Mild-level Caspase 3 immune positivity (□), IHC. Medium-level, C- (I-R) group. Medium-level, D- (IR-S)

Figure 5. A- C group. Immune negativity, B- (I) group. Mild-level, C- (I-R) group. Mild-level LC3B immune positivity (□), D- (IR-S) group. Immune negativity, IHC.

Figure 6. A- C group. Immune negativity, B- (I) group. Severe-level, C- (I-R) group. Severe-level, D- (IR-S) group. Medium-level IL-1 β immune positivity (□), IHC.

Figure 7. A- C group. Immune negativity, B- (I) group. Severe-level, C- (I-R) group. Severe-level, D- (IR-S) group. Mild-level TNF- α immune positivity (\square), IHC.

The figures demonstrate that the histopathological examination of ovarian tissues in the study drug groups, specifically concerning Caspase-3, LC3B, IL-1 β , and TNF- α staining scores, was significantly higher than those in the control staining group ($p < 0.05$). The IR-S staining group displayed significantly lower scores than the I staining group and I-R staining group ($p < 0.05$). However, there was no significant difference between the I staining group and I-R staining group in terms of Caspase-3, LC3B, IL-1 β , and TNF- α staining scores ($p > 0.05$) (Fig. 3; Fig. 4; Fig. 5; Fig. 6; Fig. 7).

Figure 8. Displays the monocyte count and monocytes cell size and the width of dispersion of rats study groups. Ischemia (I), Ischemia-Reperfusion (I-R), Ischemia-Reperfusion-Spirolactone (IR-S)

Data were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD)

^{a,b} $p < 0.05$, vs I groups and I-R groups.

^{c,d} $p < 0.05$ vs I-R groups.

The monocyte count was significantly lower in the C and IR-S notably reduced values in both the C and IR-S groups compared to the I and I-R groups ($p < 0.05$). However, compared to the I and I-R groups ($p < 0.05$). However, no in the I group, it was also lower compared to the I-R groups statistically significant distinction was observed between the I but did not reach statistical significance ($p > 0.05$). Both the and I-R groups regarding MO cell size and the width of cell size of MO and the width of dispersion counts exhibited dispersion counts ($p > 0.05$) (Fig. 8).

Table 2. Selected hematological data of study groups.

Groups	Control (n=6)	I (n=6)	IR (n=6)	IR-S (n=6)
Hematological values				
Hemoglobin(g/dL)	13.8±1.3	15.4±1.8	16.0±1.2	17.5±1.5 ^a
Hematocrit (%)	41.8±4.1	46.8±5.0	47.8±4.1	53.0±4.2 ^b
WBC (103 /uL)	7.2±2.6	6.7±1.6	5.6±1.7	7.5±2.2
Platelet (103 /μL)	705.8±374.0	691.7±337.9	737.7±167.8	1163.0±236.6 ^c
CPD monocytes cells				
[MO-X(ch)]	52.2±3.9 ^d	106.9±1.5	107.4±3.8	107.1±4.5
[MO-Y(ch)]	107.1±4.7 ^e	75.5±25.1	59.6±7.9	64.3±6.8
[MO-Z(ch)]	64.3±6.8	67.6±4.4	68.3±1.0	66.9±1.8
[MO- WX]	284.8±103.4	236.7±81.6	237.3±48.4	284.8±103.4
[MO- WY]	695.3±344.4	500.2±263.0	537.7±156.8	695.3±344.4
[MO- WZ]	467.3±29.2 ^s	506.3±68.9	568.3±25.2	467.3±29.2 ^f

Data were presented as mean ± SD as appropriate.
^{a,b,c,f} $p < 0.05$ vs Control group, I group and IR group
^{d,e} $p < 0.05$ vs. I group, IR group and IR-S group
WBC, White Blood Cells. CPD, Cell Population Data. MO-X(ch), Monocytes cells complexity. MO-Y (ch), Monocytes fluorescence intensity. MO-Z(ch), Monocytes cell size. MO-WX, Monocytes complexity and width of dispersion of the events measured. MO-WY, Monocytes fluorescence intensity and the width of dispersion. MO-WZ, Monocytes cell size and the width of dispersion

Table 2 presents the hematological parameters for C, I, I-R, and IR-S groups. Hemoglobin, hematocrit count, and platelet counts in the IR-S group were significantly higher than those in the C, I, and I-R groups ($p < 0.05$). However, there was no significant difference in other groups regarding these variables ($p > 0.05$). There was no significant difference among the study groups concerning white blood cell count, hemoglobin, hematocrit count, Monocytes cell size [MO-Z(ch)], [MO-WX], Monocytes fluorescence intensity and the width of dispersion [MO-WY] ($p > 0.05$).

The [MO-X(ch)] count in the C group was significantly lower than that in rats with I, I-R, and IR-S ($p < 0.05$). However, there

was no significant difference among I, I-R, and IR-S groups concerning these variables ($p > 0.05$). The [MO-Y(ch)] count was higher in the C group compared to rats in the I, I-R, and IR-S groups ($p < 0.05$). However, in the rats with I, I-R, and IR-S groups, it did not reach statistical significance ($p > 0.05$). The [MO-Y(ch)] count was significantly lower in the C group compared to rats in the I, I-R, and IR-S groups ($p < 0.05$). However, in the rats with I, I-R, and IR-S groups, it did not reach statistical significance ($p > 0.05$). The monocytes cell size and the width of dispersion [MO-WZ] count in the IR-S group was significantly lower than that in rats with I and IR groups ($p < 0.05$). However, there was no significant difference between I and I-R groups regarding the [MO-WZ] count ($p > 0.05$).

DISCUSSION

According to the findings of the histological examination, ovarian edema and hemorrhage were reduced by spironolactone. The use of spironolactone resulted in a decrease in histopathological indications of substances released from the tissue, macrophage activity (indicators of cell death), as well as a reduction in IL-1 β and TNF- α , indicators of inflammation, in the tissue. The study highlights the potential protective effect of spironolactone against IRI in rat ovaries. In the spironolactone-administered group, a lower MO count in the hematological parameters for both I and I-R was observed, approaching values seen in the C group. Overall, spironolactone was found to lead to a reduction in the MO count and cell population data. This suggests that when these medications are administered to patients suspected of ovarian torsion, they may help prevent further damage to the ovary until a definitive diagnosis is made and after the diagnosis. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study on cell population data and spironolactone in the context of ovarian ischemic reperfusion in rats.

Spironolactone, a well-known aldosterone receptor antagonist primarily used as a diuretic and anti-hypertensive agent, has additional anti-inflammatory actions that may contribute to dampening the inflammatory response. Spironolactone's ability to induce vasodilation is often associated with its influence on endothelial function^{10,15,16}. Extensively utilized in clinical practice^{17,18}, spironolactone has been the subject of numerous research studies assessing its efficacy in managing IRI in organs such as the kidneys and heart through clinical investigations. The outcomes from these studies have consistently demonstrated the advantageous impacts of this medication^{19,20}.

In I-R models, various experimental investigations on tissues other than the liver have indicated that spironolactone possesses anti-inflammatory properties (9); Mejía-Vilet et al.²¹ conducted an investigation to explore the potential of spironolactone administration in mitigating the functional and structural impairments caused by renal I-R. They found that the benefits provided by spironolactone were identified through its capacity to diminish oxidative stress. This was demonstrated by a decrease in lipoperoxidation within the kidneys, elevated expression of antioxidant enzymes, and a revival of urinary excretion of nitric oxide (NO)₂/NO. They

suggested that spironolactone plays a central role in this model of renal injury.

Atalay et al.²² investigated the antioxidant effects of spironolactone to assess its potential protective effects in hepatic IRI. They demonstrated that spironolactone provided protection against I-R induced harm by significantly diminishing the adverse effects. They suggested that spironolactone treatment can significantly reduce the morbidity and mortality associated with hepatic ischemia by mitigating ischemia-induced oxidative stress, organ injury, and dysfunction caused by free radicals.

Barut et al.²³ examined the impact of the aldosterone receptor blocker spironolactone on lung injury resulting from intestinal I-R. They found that spironolactone pretreatment significantly decreased lung injury caused by intestinal IRI, as evidenced by histological observations and reductions in lipid peroxidation and myeloperoxidase levels. Furthermore, this pretreatment led to a decrease in the immunoreactivity of inducible NO synthase. They strongly suggest that spironolactone pretreatment decreased the harming model of intestinal I-R induced lung injury in rats.

Spironolactone has been observed to decrease the activity of myeloperoxidase in the context of inflammatory events through its ability to scavenge free radicals²⁴. One of the hallmarks of IRI is increased apoptosis, which can lead to tissue injury and dysfunction. Spironolactone's potential to modulate apoptotic pathways might be pivotal in preventing excessive cell death following reperfusion. Considering the positive effects of spironolactone on hematological parameters used in our study, these elevated blood parameters may lead to increased tissue oxygenation, resulting in reduced tissue damage. When all these studies are considered, it is understood that our findings conform with the literature.

Ischemia and subsequent reperfusion can disrupt microvascular circulation, leading to tissue hypoxia and inflammation. Spironolactone's vasodilatory effects, attributed to its impact on endothelial function²⁵, might help maintain microvascular perfusion in the ovaries during the reperfusion phase. This, in turn, could contribute to reduced tissue damage and improved recovery. Our study demonstrated that while the induction of ovarian ischemia caused reduced MO infiltration and an associated significant increase in Caspase-3, LC3B

staining compared to the I group and I-R group, Caspase-3, LC3B staining scores were significantly lowered in the spironolactone-administered group, approaching that in the I group and I-R group. Various studies have been conducted on the relationship between ovarian I-R and key molecular markers, including Caspase-3, LC3B, TNF- α , and IL-1 β . In addition to the elevation of Caspase-3, an apoptotic marker, it has been reported that the levels of LC3B, an autophagic marker, increase in I-R^{25,26}. Similarly, studies have indicated an elevation in the levels of cytokines such as TNF- α and IL-1 β in I-R^{3,25,26}.

Oxidative stress and inflammation can trigger a series of events that ultimately result in programmed cell death, known as apoptosis. This process involves a cascade of cellular events, with key molecules such as Bcl-2, Caspase 9, and most notably, Caspase 3, playing crucial roles. Among these, Caspase 3 emerges as a pivotal molecule during the progression towards cell death, orchestrating various steps in the apoptotic pathway²⁷. In our study, the observed reduction in high levels of Caspase-3 expression in response to Spironolactone administration has been interpreted as the anti-apoptotic effect of Spironolactone. This finding is consistent with studies reporting elevated Caspase-3 expression in I-R conditions^{3,25,28}. Gungor et al.²⁹ conducted a study to investigate the impact of hesperidin on ovarian IRI. They observed an elevation in the reactivity of Caspase 3 in both the I and I-R groups. This supports our results as the administration of treatment groups has demonstrated a significant decrease in the expression of caspase 3. Similar to our findings, an I-R study showed that astaxanthin (ASX) decreases Caspase 3 levels³⁰.

LC3B serves as a crucial marker in autophagic cell death, another pathway of cell demise³¹. Although studies on LC3B are limited, investigations have revealed elevated levels of LC3B in I-R, consistent with our findings^{26,27}. In our study, the decrease in LC3B levels with Spironolactone usage has been interpreted as evidence of Spironolactone's anti-autophagic property, suggesting a protective effect against I-R.

TNF- α and IL-1 β are markers that emerge during inflammation³². These two markers, closely related to each other, involve IL-1 β synthesized from mononuclear cells, which in turn increases TNF- α synthesis³³. Studies have reported an elevation in TNF- α and IL-1 β levels during I-R, with a subsequent decrease in levels upon the use of

antioxidants, indicating their anti-inflammatory effects³⁴.

Adnexal torsion leads to a decrease in blood flow and elevates levels of lactic acid, hypoxanthine, and lipid peroxides. While detorsion is employed as a treatment for adnexal torsion, it results in neutrophil infiltration and an uptick in the production of free oxygen radicals and TNF α , as well as cytokines like NO³⁵. Dincer et al.³² aim to investigate the biochemical, molecular, and histopathological dimensions of ovarian IRI and assess whether gossypin could offer beneficial effects in mitigating its effects. They found a decrease in TNF- α and IL-1 β . They suggest that gossypin protects ovarian tissue. Geyikoglu et al.²⁸ examined the impact of boric acid and propolis on injury caused by I-R in the study. The researchers assessed the levels of TNF- α through immunohistochemical analyses. The results revealed that the utilization of these substances in treatment led to a reduction in the elevated protein levels of TNF- α induced by I-R. In our study, while TNF- α and IL-1 β levels were determined to be high in the I-R group, a decrease in TNF- α and IL-1 β levels was observed in the group treated with Spironolactone. This observation indicates the anti-inflammatory property of Spironolactone in the context of I-R.

Buoro et al.³⁶ assessed the clinical importance of the parameters derived from cell population data collected from septic patients admitted to the intensive care unit. They found that neutrophils and MO fluorescence intensity values were significantly elevated in patients with septic shock compared to those with sepsis or individuals who did not develop sepsis. They suggested that certain new sets of data related to cell populations could offer valuable insights for diagnosing and treating sepsis. In our study, a general decrease was observed in the MO subgroup and in the cell population data, which could be attributed to the anti-inflammatory effect of spironolactone³⁷. Overall, our current knowledge and findings suggest that spironolactone may protect the ovarian against IRI contributes. The findings of this study have potential clinical implications. While the study focused on rat ovaries, extrapolating these results to human ovaries could open avenues for novel strategies in protecting ovarian function.

Limitations: It's important to acknowledge the limitations of this study. The rat model used in the study may not perfectly mirror the complexity of human ovarian physiology, and the precise dose-response relationship of spironolactone requires further investigation.

In conclusion, the findings elucidated within this study propose that spironolactone confers a protective influence against IRI within rat ovaries. Its anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and potential vasodilatory properties, along with its ability to modulate apoptosis, make it a promising candidate for further exploration as a protective agent in ovarian IRI. Spironolactone may present novel avenues for safeguarding the ovarian against IRI.

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